

ISic1363

I.Sicily inscription 1363

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Catania, inventory 288

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ἐνθάδε
2. κεῖται Οὐρ
3. σουλος ζή
4. [σα]ς ἔτη κη μῆ
5. [νας] ς ἡμέρ(ας) η τελ
6. [ευτᾱ] καλ(ανδαῖς) Αὐγ(ούσταις)

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004

Translation (en)

Here lies Oursoulos, having lived for 28 years, 6 months, and 8 days. For his death in the Kalends of August

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492977

EDCS 39101743

PHI 140868

PHI 316282

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. *Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0544 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Korhonen, K. 2004. *Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione.* Helsinki. At 202

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Wessel, C. 1989. *Inscriptiones Graecae Christianae Veteres Occidentis. Inscriptiones Christianae Italiae.* Bari. At 1374

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